

PRESS RELEASES
DISTRIBUTION SERVICE

MOST TRUSTED NEWSWIRE PRESS RELEASE DISTRIBUTION

**CELEBRATING OVER TEN YEARS (2005-2015) SERVING
THE NEWS DISTRIBUTION MARKET**

HOME | ABOUT NEWSWIRETODAY | TOP ARTICLES | TELL A FRIEND | CONTACT/LIVE CHAT | INVESTORS | **PREMIUM DISTRIBUTION / PRICING** | SIGN UP FREE! | SUBMIT NEWS RELEASE

More news: Electronics / Instrumentation / RFID
Written by / Agency / Source: *Imec*

Follow @NewsWireTODAY | Check Ads Availability | e-mail Article

Are you the owner of this article?, Turn it PREMIUM with your LOGO instead - and make it 3rd party Ads-Free! within the next hour!

Imec, TNO and Cartamundi Develop Flexible Tags that Communicate with Standard Touch Screens

NewsWireToday - /newswire/ - **Leuven, Belgium, 2019/12/17** - Breakthrough IoT technology for IoT applications featured on cover of Nature Electronics - TNO.nl / Cartamundi.com / imec-int.com.

YOUR BANNER AD HERE INSTEAD - SHOWING ALONG WITH ALL ARTICLES COVERING ELECTRONICS / INSTRUMENTATION / RFID ANNOUNCEMENTS

Replace these Affiliate Programs at ANYTIME! Your banner here within the next hour. [Learn How!](#)

DRIVE MASSIVE TRAFFIC TO YOUR WEBSITE NOW

Interactieive Digital Signage

Touchscreen Displays

Interactieive digital signage displays met touchscreen.
touchwalls.be

OPENEN

Imec, a world-leading research and innovation hub in nanoelectronics and digital technologies, TNO (tno.nl), and Cartamundi (cartamundi.com) announced that they have developed a flexible capacitive identification tag that communicates with standard touch screens (C-touch). C-touch tags can be integrated in a wide range of paper and plastic based objects such as tickets, certified documents, payment cards, realizing smart products. The connection to the internet is established simply by placing the tagged object on the touchscreen or vice-versa. The results, developed in the framework of Holst Centre, an open innovation initiative by imec and TNO, were published in this week's Nature Electronics.

C-touch tags are thin and flexible chips that can be integrated in paper and plastic products. They have a unique identifier which can communicate via any touchscreen. Smart cards or other objects with embedded C-touch tags can securely interact with the 4.5 billion mobile phones used worldwide, as well as with the large number of touch screens now being integrated in cars, booths,

walls, coffee machines and all sorts of everyday objects. Without requiring additional hardware and major reconfigurations or additional costs for the users, C-touch tags provide a solution to label trillions of everyday objects to truly create the Internet-of-Everything. These tags offer security thanks to the very short communication range; general compatibility thanks to the presence of capacitive touchscreens everywhere; and the potential to be produced at low cost thanks to the monolithically integrated antenna. Compared to existing RFID technologies such as NFC, the new C-touch tag does not require an external antenna. The tiny antenna is part of the chip itself, making the tag much smaller compared to current NFC tags. The small size enables integration into everyday objects. Thus, C-touch tags are an alternative in all those use cases where interaction via touchscreens is feasible, but RFID/NFC tags are either too large or too expensive or where contactless reading is a disadvantage. For example, in board games where cost is discriminator, to provide higher security in payment cards, or to replace difficult to service and manage hardware readers and access control points with easy to

service and update apps on standard mobile devices, etc.

The new C-touch tag that imec (imec-int.com), TNO and their partners have described in Nature Electronics is based on thin-film transistor technology and is powered by a thin-film battery or a thin-film photovoltaic cell that converts light from the touchscreen. The 12-bit thin-film capacitive identification tag achieves up to 36bps data transfer rates at 0.6V supply voltage, which is compatible with commercially available touchscreen devices without requiring modifications. The flexible thin-film integrated circuit has a 0.8cm² on-chip monolithic antenna and dissipates only 38nW of power at 600mV supply voltage.

“Our C-touch tag paves the way to a multitude of new applications compared to standard RFID or NFC solutions as it takes advantage of the widespread availability of touchscreen readers compared to the limited amount of NFC readers,” says Kris Myny, principal scientist and R&D team leader at imec. “We are testing the tag system and communication method using a range of different touchscreens from a variety of brands, including Apple, Samsung and Huawei.”

“These tags provide new possibilities of connecting objects to internet and enabling Internet-of-Everything. Our next steps will be to further improve the performance of the tags, enable new features such as bi-directional communication with touchscreens, and work with companies in developing solutions based on C-touch tags in different application domains”, says Prashant Agrawal, program manager for thin film electronics at imec.

Steven Nietvelt, CTO of Cartamundi says: “We are very excited to be part of this project. The C-touch tages will enable us to even further blur the boundaries between digital and physical gaming and unlocks exciting new consumer experiences.”

This project was executed in the framework of Holst Centre, an open innovation initiative by imec and TNO. It has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, project CAPID, under grant agreement No 732389, the ERC project FLICs, under grant agreement No 716426 and through the Flexlines project within the Interreg V-programme Flanders-The Netherlands, a cross-border cooperation programme with financial support from the European Regional Development Fund, and co-financed by the Province of Noord-Brabant, The Netherlands.

YOUR BANNER AD HERE INSTEAD - SHOWING ALONG WITH ALL ARTICLES COVERING ELECTRONICS / INSTRUMENTATION / RFID ANNOUNCEMENTS

Replace these Affiliate Programs at ANYTIME! Your banner here within the next hour. [Learn How!](#)

Written by / Agency / Source: *Imec*

Availability: All Regions (Including Int'l)

Traffic Booster: Quick NewswireToday Visibility Checker

Distribution / Indexing: / [Company listed above is a registered member of our network. Content made possible by PRZOOM / PRTODAY indexing services]

###

Your Banner Ad showing on ALL Electronics / Instrumentation / RFID articles, CATCH Visitors via Your Competitors Announcements!

Company website links NOT available to basic submissions

It is OK to republish and/or LINK any newswire for any legitimate media purpose as long as you name **NewswireToday** and **LINK** as the source.

Is this your article?
 Activate ALL web links and social stream by Upgrading to Press Release PREMIUM Plan Now!
FLEXIBLE TAGS | IMEC

Publisher Contact: **Hanne Degans - imec.be**
■ hanne.degans[@]imec.be

Newswire Today - PRZOOM / PRTODAY disclaims any content contained in this article. If you need/wish to contact the company who published the current release, you will need to contact them - NOT us. Issuers of articles are solely responsible for the accuracy of their content. Our complete disclaimer appears here.

IMPORTANT INFORMATION: Issuance, publication or distribution of this press release in certain jurisdictions could be subject to restrictions. The recipient of this press release is responsible for using this press release and the information herein in accordance

with the applicable rules and regulations in the particular jurisdiction. This press release does not constitute an offer or an offering to acquire or subscribe for any Imec securities in any jurisdiction including any other companies listed or named in this release.

Electronics / Instrumentation / RFID via RSS [NewswireTODAY](#) [PRZOOM FEED](#)

Find who Retweet Follow @NewswireTODAY

| [e-mail Article](#)

Are you the owner of this article?, Turn it PREMIUM with your LOGO instead - and make it 3rd party Ads-Free! within the next hour!

[READ LATEST ARTICLES FROM IMEC / COMPANY PROFILE](#)

Read Electronics / Instrumentation / RFID Most Recent Related Newswires:

- Wilson Electronics' weBoost Home Complete Named as CES 2020 Innovation Awards Honoree
- Cobham Announces QML Q/Q+ Qualification of their RadTolerant Microcontroller
- MadgeTech Releases New, Streamlined Solution for Shock Monitoring
- Thales Technology Enables Fisheries Science Research on New Canadian Coast Guard Vessel
- Retelit and Eurotech Collaborate for A New Ecosystem of IoT Platforms and Infrastructures
- BIOS Updates for Kontron ATX Motherboards 'Designed by Fujitsu'
- HUBER+SUHNER Launches Lightest and Most Compact Cable Yet, Revolutionising Offshore Connectivity
- Imec Presents Forksheet Device as the Ultimate Solution to Push Scaling Towards the 2nm Technology Node
- Eurotech Named Best in Class in 'IoT Platforms Based On Open Source' by Market Research and Strategic Consultancy PAC (teknowlogy Group)
- Curtiss-Wright Announces New NVIDIA® Quadro® Turing™ TU104/106 GPGPU Processor Modules for ISR/EW and AI Applications
- HUBER+SUHNER Introduces SENCITY® Occhio MIMO 4x4 Antenna
- Eurotech Collaborates with Microsoft to Accelerate Internet of Things Solutions
- Curtiss-Wright Defense Solutions to Expand Position in U.S. Navy Shipbuilding and Upgrade Markets with Acquisition of 901D Holdings, LLC
- SPI Lasers Launches VariMODE Adaptable Laser Beams
- Kontron Adds the New KBox C-103-CFL Series to its Industrial Computer Family

©2019 NewswireToday — Limelon Advertising, Co. [Home](#) | [About](#) | [Advertise/Pricing](#) | [Contact](#) | [Investors](#) | [Privacy/TOS](#) | [Sitemap](#) | [FRANCAIS](#)

newswire, PR press releases distribution service magazines engine news alert newsroom press room breaking news public relations articles company news alerts newswiredistribution ezine bizentrepreneur biznewstoday digital business report market search pr firms agencies reports distri-bution today investor relation successful internet entrepreneurs newswire distribution prtoday.com newswiredistribution asianewstoday bizwiretoday USA pr UK today - NOT affiliated with PRNewswire as we declined their partnership offer in 2013

PRTODAY & NewswireTODAY are NOT affiliated with USA TODAY ([usatoday.com](#))